

**A REVIEW OF FACTORS INFLUENCING LEARNERS' GAIN OF
ENGLISH PROFICIENCY**

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Abstract: Different factors are involved in the process of learners learning English as a second or foreign language. Some contribute to enhancing their English proficiency, others mitigate and or even delay the process of learners' mastering the language. Throughout literature, many studies focus on one or several factors that have an impact on learners' gain of English language proficiency. Few studies have been conducted to explore groups of factors together. The paper also implies what different stakeholders can do to maximize and optimize learners' gain and progress in English language learning.

Keywords: learners, English proficiency, influencing factors, progress

English has become an international language and been used popularly in many areas of life all over the world. Therefore, people of different ages and nationalities have been learning English for communicating with others, learning abroad, looking for jobs, entertaining, and so on. However, while some people can acquire English easily, others have been struggling to learn the so – called lingua – franca. Across literature on English language teaching and learning, researchers conducted different studies to explore individual factors that have an impact on learners' English proficiency levels. However, almost no studies have been implemented to synthesize all such factors together. Meanwhile, such a review of influencing factors will raise the awareness of learners, teachers and researchers of the English language as well as help them optimize the favorable factors and mitigate the negative ones. The current review is such an attempt.

The level of learners' English language proficiency is significantly influenced by various factors related to learners themselves. These factors include learners' learning autonomy, learners' motivation and attitudes to English language learning, and learners' learning strategies.

Language learning process not only is affected by internal factors, which learners bring with them to the particular situation, but also relies in a number of different external factors (Madrid, 1995; Shoe – bottom, 2016). The key factor that has a great impact on learners' learning progress is teachers (Geringer, 2003). In English language teaching, the influencing factors related to the teachers' pedagogical knowledge and skills, teacher' teaching approaches, assessment and giving feedback.

Teacher quality id considered to be the most important teacher – related factor that influence learners' learning outcomes (Punthunasen, 2007). The issue of teacher quality has been approached differently by various researcher and educators in the field. Some of them remark that command of the subject area, appropriate teaching methods, and different teaching – related skills represent teaching characteristics. Others focus on personal characteristics, their compassion, humor, innovation, and honesty (Flowerdew et al., 2007). Although in general, good teachers share similar qualities regardless of their disciplines, effective teachers are vitally different from other teachers because of nature of English as a teaching subject (Al – Mahrooqi et al., 2015).

CONCLUSION

Further studies should be conducted to explore which factors have the strongest positive correlations with students' English proficiency gain. Different contexts and student subjects field different findings, which makes the whole picture of the topic even clearer provides more useful implications for related stakeholders.

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